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Instructional Leadership and Teaching Competence: A Study of Master Teachers in Dapitan City National High School

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ABSTRACT: This study aimed to determine the instructional leadership practices and teaching competence of teachers in Dapitan City National High School, Schools Division of Dapitan City, during School Year 2025–2026. The respondents of the study were ninety-five (95) respondents from the main campus and extension schools. The study employed a survey descriptive-correlational research design using an adopted questionnaire checklist. Weighted mean, standard deviation, and Spearman rank-order correlation were used in analyzing the data. The teachers' perceived level of instructional leadership practices was also very high, particularly in personal growth and professional development, planning, assessment, and reporting, and curriculum content and pedagogy. Likewise, their teaching competence was very high in subject matter skills, teaching strategies skills, classroom management skills, and evaluation skills. Results further showed that instructional leadership practices were strongly, positively, and significantly related to teaching competence. It was concluded that teachers who demonstrate stronger instructional leadership practices also tend to exhibit higher teaching competence. Based on the findings, it is recommended that DepEd District and Division Officials strengthen division-based training, coaching, mentoring, and professional development programs that focus on improving instructional leadership and teaching competence. School Heads/Principals are encouraged to establish regular monitoring, peer mentoring, Learning Action Cell sessions, and technical assistance activities to sustain teachers' high instructional performance.

KEYWORDS: instructional leadership practices, teaching competence, curriculum content and pedagogy, planning assessment and reporting, professional development, Schools Division of Dapitan City, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Master Teachers are career-stage teachers recognized for their demonstrated instructional excellence and their capacity to extend their impact beyond their own classrooms through mentoring and instructional support. They occupy a distinctive “hybrid” role in schools because they remain active classroom practitioners while also serving as instructional leaders who model effective teaching, coach colleagues, and help strengthen school-wide teaching and learning processes. In Philippine public secondary school settings, this instructional leadership is commonly enacted through coaching, demonstration or model lessons, and professional collaboration, positioning Master Teachers as key drivers of instructional improvement across grade levels and subject areas. Arombo (2023) underscores that Master Teachers can simultaneously demonstrate high levels of instructional competence, including subject mastery, teaching strategies, classroom management, assessment, and mentoring, alongside strong instructional leadership practices. This shows how excellence in teaching and leadership can coexist within one professional position. In the same vein, Baldera (2025) emphasizes that Master Teachers' influence is often relational and built through sustained mentoring and shared practice, which reinforces the importance of studying their instructional leadership and teaching competence to understand how improvements in classroom instruction are strengthened and maintained at the school level.

Teaching competence refers to a teacher's ability to plan lessons, deliver instruction, manage the classroom, assess learning, and build positive relationships with learners to support effective learning outcomes. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (2017) emphasized that teaching competence is anchored on the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, which include content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and professional growth. Similarly, König et al. (2021) found that teachers' pedagogical competence is significantly associated with instructional quality, indicating that competent teachers are better able to organize lessons, apply appropriate teaching strategies, manage classroom processes, and respond to learners' academic needs. Thus, teaching competence is not limited to mastery of the subject matter but also includes the effective use of instructional skills, classroom management, assessment practices, and learner-centered approaches that promote meaningful teaching and learning.

Research on effective professional development emphasizes that improvements in teaching practice are more likely when learning opportunities are content-focused, sustained, and supported through coaching, feedback, and reflection—features that closely match what Master

Teachers are expected to provide as mentors and instructional leaders. Based on the researcher's own experiences and classroom observations, teachers tend to demonstrate greater confidence and consistency in lesson delivery when Master Teachers conduct demonstration teaching, provide coaching conversations, and give timely and specific feedback on lesson planning, classroom management, and assessment practices. However, the availability and quality of this support often vary across schools and teaching contexts, resulting in uneven implementation of instructional strategies and assessment routines. This observed reality reinforces the value of structured and well-designed professional learning, as Darling-Hammond et al. (2017) stress that effective professional development strengthens teachers' instructional expertise and supports consistent classroom implementation. In the same way, Kraft et al. (2018) show that coaching produces meaningful improvements in instructional practice and can contribute to student gains. This supports the researcher's observation that Master Teachers' mentoring and coaching should be treated as a practical and scalable mechanism for strengthening teaching competence across classrooms.

Conceptually and empirically, instructional leadership and teaching competence are expected to move together because leadership for learning shapes the conditions under which teachers refine their practice through instructional guidance, professional learning support, and feedback cycles connected to classroom work. Nguyen et al. (2020) reported positive relationships between instructional leadership dimensions, such as monitoring learning and promoting professional development, and teacher competence dimensions, indicating that leadership behaviors can align with stronger pedagogical and assessment-related capacities. Similarly, He et al. (2024) showed that principals' instructional leadership predicts teachers' professional development, supporting the idea that leadership practices oriented toward teaching and learning can foster continuous competence-building.

Based on the researcher's experiences and classroom observations, most teachers are generally cooperative and committed to their responsibilities. They perform their duties well, fulfill assigned tasks, and demonstrate professionalism in teaching and school activities. However, there are instances when a few teachers do not comply with or respond promptly to instructions and agreed schedules, which can affect coordination and the smooth implementation of school programs. These situations are often observed during deadlines, reporting schedules, or shared activities where teamwork and timely cooperation are needed. Overall, while the teaching workforce demonstrates strong performance and dedication, strengthening consistent compliance, communication, and accountability among all teachers remains important to sustain effective school operations and support continuous improvement in teaching and learning.

A clear research gap exists in the instructional leadership literature because much of the empirical evidence remains concentrated on school principals or on broadly defined forms of teacher leadership. Prior studies continue to note conceptual and methodological challenges in linking teacher leadership roles to clearly measured instructional outcomes. In the Philippine context, recent work has started to document how Master Teachers enact instructional leadership and develop a leader-teacher identity. However, this evidence is still largely descriptive and qualitative, and it has not sufficiently established how Master Teachers' instructional leadership practices relate to measurable indicators of teaching competence. Additionally, many quantitative studies examining leadership-competence relationships are drawn from other national settings and are not specific to the Master Teacher position, which limits the direct applicability of findings to DepEd-defined roles, expectations, and professional standards. Therefore, there is a need for context-specific quantitative research that examines and measures the relationship between Master Teachers' instructional leadership and teaching competence to provide localized evidence for strengthening mentoring systems, professional learning design, and instructional improvement initiatives.

LITERATURE

Instructional leadership

Instructional leadership is consistently described in recent scholarship as leadership that centers on the "core business" of schools teaching and learning by aligning curriculum, instruction, assessment, and professional learning toward clear learning goals. Hallinger (2025) shows that instructional leadership studies increasingly emphasize instructional guidance, monitoring of teaching-learning processes, and building learning-focused school conditions, reflecting the model's enduring usefulness for examining leadership that directly targets classroom practice. Similarly, Nwosu (2022) synthesizes post-pandemic literature and argues that strengthening instructional leadership is critical for improving learner achievement because it mobilizes instructional support systems such as coaching, supervision, and teacher professional learning mechanisms that are closely tied to sustaining instructional quality.

Curriculum Content and Pedagogy

Research highlights that curriculum content and pedagogy is a foundational domain of teacher quality because it requires both mastery of subject matter and the skill to translate that knowledge into developmentally appropriate, meaningful instruction aligned with curriculum standards. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd) through the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers emphasizes that effective practice begins with strong content knowledge applied within and across curriculum areas, supported by research-based principles of teaching and learning (DepEd, 2017). Darling-Hammond, Hylar, and Gardner (2017) synthesize evidence showing that professional development is most effective when it is content-focused linking teaching strategies to specific curriculum content because it strengthens teachers' pedagogical decisions and improves classroom implementation of standards-based instruction.

Planning, Assessment, and Reporting

Literature underscores that planning, assessment, and reporting are core instructional functions that ensure teaching is intentional, evidence-based, and responsive to learner needs. In the Philippine setting, the Department of Education institutionalized these expectations through the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, particularly Domain 5 (Assessment and Reporting), which emphasizes designing and using appropriate assessment strategies, monitoring learner progress, providing feedback to improve learning, communicating results to stakeholders, and using assessment data to enhance teaching practices (DepEd, 2017). International evidence likewise shows that classroom assessment and timely feedback are routine practices linked to stronger instructional decision-making; the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development reported in TALIS 2018 results that large proportions of teachers regularly assess student progress through observation and provide

immediate feedback, highlighting assessment as an integral part of daily teaching and reporting cycles that support learning improvement (OECD, 2019).

Personal Growth and Professional Development

Recent literature frames personal growth and professional development as a core requirement for sustaining effective teaching because it emphasizes continuous learning, reflective practice, and purposeful career development anchored on professional standards. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017) institutionalized this through the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), Domain 7, which highlights teachers' commitment to professional reflection, collegial learning, and setting development goals as part of improving practice across career stages. The Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019) reports from TALIS 2018 that continuous professional development is a key dimension of teacher professionalism, and that ongoing learning opportunities across a teacher's career are essential for strengthening instructional knowledge and skills in changing classroom contexts.

Teaching Competence

Teaching competence is widely framed as a professional capability that combines what teachers know, can do, and value in order to deliver quality instruction and improve learner outcomes. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017) formalized this view through the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), which specifies competence expectations across domains such as content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, curriculum and planning, assessment and reporting, and professional growth. Similarly, Guerriero (2017) explains that teacher competence is rooted in the pedagogical core of the profession—how teachers use pedagogical knowledge to make sound instructional decisions and connect teaching knowledge to practice, which is closely tied to student learning.

Teaching competence is not only a set of teacher dispositions (e.g., content and pedagogical knowledge) but also includes situation-specific skills that shape instructional quality and student learning progress. Blömeke (2022) demonstrated an “effect chain” where teachers' knowledge relates to students' learning progression through teachers' skills and the instructional quality they enact in class, highlighting competence as observable in planning, teaching decisions, and classroom implementation. In addition, evidence on teacher learning shows that competence strengthens when teachers engage in well-designed professional development; Darling-Hammond, Hylar, and Gardner (2017) synthesize findings that effective professional development is content-focused, includes active learning and coaching/feedback, and supports classroom implementation—features that build teachers' instructional competence over time.

Subject Matter Skills

Recent literature emphasizes that subject matter skills are a foundational component of teaching quality because teachers must possess deep and accurate understanding of what they teach in order to explain concepts clearly, address misconceptions, and connect lessons to curriculum standards. In the Philippine setting, the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017) highlights this in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, particularly Domain 1 (Content Knowledge and Pedagogy), which stresses teachers' mastery of content knowledge and its application within and across curriculum areas as a core expectation of professional practice. Likewise, the Organisation for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD, 2019) underscores in TALIS 2018 results that teachers are expected to have a deep and broad understanding of what they teach because teacher knowledge strongly shapes classroom instruction and student learning, reinforcing subject matter skills as a critical competency for effective teaching.

Teaching Strategies Skills

Recent literature underscores that teaching strategies skills refer to a teacher's capacity to select and apply appropriate, research-informed methods that actively engage learners, differentiate instruction, and align learning activities with intended outcomes. Darling-Hammond, Hylar, and Gardner (2017) emphasize that teaching improves when teachers develop and practice instructional strategies that are content-focused and grounded in active learning such as modeling, collaborative lesson design, and classroom application with feedback because these strengthen how teachers translate standards into effective classroom instruction. In addition, evidence from coaching research shows that sustained instructional support sharpens teachers' day-to-day strategy use; Kraft, Blazar, and Hogan (2018) found that coaching interventions produce meaningful improvements in instructional practice, suggesting that teachers' strategic skill grows through guided practice, feedback, and refinement of classroom techniques over time.

Classroom Management Skills

Classroom management skills as a critical component of teaching effectiveness because they help teachers establish orderly learning environments, prevent or reduce disruptive behavior, and maximize time on task, which in turn supports students' academic and socio-emotional outcomes. In a large meta-analysis, Korpershoek et al. (2016) found that classroom management strategies and programs produce positive effects on students' academic, behavioral, emotional, and motivational outcomes, underscoring that effective management is not merely disciplinary but instructionally consequential. Likewise, a systematic review of classroom management research trends by Bozkuş (2021) highlights that classroom management remains a central competency required for effective teaching, particularly because it shapes the learning climate and enables teachers to implement instructional strategies consistently.

Evaluation Skills

Evaluation skills (often discussed as teachers' *assessment literacy*) involve the ability to design or select appropriate assessment tools, apply clear criteria and scoring, interpret evidence of learning, provide timely feedback, and use results to improve instruction and report progress accurately. In the Philippine context, the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017) highlights these competencies in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers (PPST), Domain 5 (Assessment and Reporting), which underscores monitoring and evaluating learner progress, giving feedback to improve learning, communicating results to stakeholders, and using assessment data to enhance teaching practice. Complementing this policy-based view, a systematic review by Pastore et al. (2023) notes that teachers commonly experience difficulties translating assessment principles into classroom practice, reinforcing the need to strengthen teachers' evaluative capacities especially in interpreting evidence, aligning assessments with learning goals, and using assessment information for instructional decisions.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is illustrated in Figure 1. Part I highlights the independent variable, instructional leadership which is measured through three indicators, namely: curriculum content and pedagogy, planning, assessment, and reporting, and personal growth and professional development. This section consists of thirty (30) items designed to assess the level of instructional leadership. Part II presents the dependent variable, teaching competence, which is evaluated based on the four indicators, namely: subject matter skills, teaching strategies skills, classroom management skills, and evaluation skills.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

Statement of the Problem

This study aimed to determine the instructional leadership and teaching competence of master teachers in Dapitan City National High during the school year 2025-2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' perceived level of instructional leadership in terms of:
 - 1.1 curriculum content and pedagogy;
 - 1.2 planning, assessment, and reporting; and
 - 1.3 personal growth and professional development?
2. What is the respondents' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of:
 - 2.1 subject matter skills;
 - 2.2 teaching strategies skills;
 - 2.3 classroom management skills; and
 - 2.4 evaluation skills?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' perceived level of Instructional leadership practices and the respondents' perceived level of teaching competence?

Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the respondents' perceived level of Instructional leadership practices and the respondents' perceived level of teaching competence.

Scope and Limitations of the Study

This study focuses on determining the level of instructional leadership and teaching competence and examining the relationship between these two variables among 95 teacher-respondents of Dapitan City National High School, Schools Division of Dapitan City, during School Year 2025–2026.

This study is limited to two major variables: instructional leadership and teaching competence. Instructional leadership is measured through three indicators, namely curriculum content and pedagogy; planning, assessment, and reporting; and personal growth and professional development. On the other hand, teaching competence is evaluated based on four indicators, namely subject matter skills, teaching strategies skills, classroom management skills, and evaluation skills.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Method Used

The study utilized survey and descriptive-correlational research methods. The researcher used the survey method to collect data on instructional leadership and teaching competence through a questionnaire. Hellevik (2019) explains that in quantitative questionnaire surveys, “the same questions are presented to a relatively large sample” of respondents, usually with fixed response options, which supports efficient data collection and comparability across participants. Likewise, McCombes (2019/2025) defines survey research as collecting information about a group by asking questions and analyzing the results, underscoring why surveys are practical for generating large amounts of data efficiently. Creswell and Guetterman (2019) define correlational research as the systematic investigation of relationships among two or more variables without any experimental manipulation of those variables. Correlational research is a non-experimental approach in which the researcher quantifies variables and assesses the statistical relationship between instructional leadership and teaching competence without manipulating or controlling the variables.

Research Instrument

The questionnaire used in the study consisted of two parts: Part I: Instructional Leadership adopted from Mendoza, J. J., & Bautista, S. C. (2019), with three indicators, namely: curriculum content and pedagogy; planning, assessment, and reporting; and personal growth and professional development; Part II: teaching Competence adopted from Mendoza, J. J., & Bautista, S. C. (2019), with four indicators, namely: subject matter skills; teaching strategies skills; classroom management skills; and Evaluation Skills.

Ethical Consideration

This study secured approval from the Research and Ethics Committee of the Department of Education before the conduct of data gathering. Informed consent was obtained from the institution and the individual respondents prior to their participation. The questionnaire was written in clear and understandable language to ensure voluntary and informed participation. The identities of the respondents were kept anonymous, and all information gathered was treated with strict confidentiality. Only essential research data were retained for academic and future research purposes.

Statistical Treatment of the Data

Presented below are the statistical tools utilized in the treatment and analysis of the data gathered.

Weighted Mean. This is used to quantify the respondents’ ratings on the Instructional Leadership and Teaching Competence.

Scoring Procedure

Instructional Leadership and Teaching Competence			
Scale	Range of Values	Description	Interpretation
5	4.21-5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High
4	3.41-4.20	Agree	High
3	2.61-3.40	Somewhat Agree	Average
2	1.81-2.60	Disagree	Low
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree	Very Low

Standard Deviation. This is used to determine the homogeneity and heterogeneity of the employee's score, where $SD \leq 3$ is homogenous and $SD > 3$ is heterogeneous Aiken & Susane (2001); Refugio et al. (2019).

Spearman Rank-Order Correlation Coefficient (Spearman rho). This is used to determine the correlation between instructional leadership and teaching Competence. The following guide in interpreting the correlation value proposed by Cohen et al. (2014) was utilized in this study:

Value	Size	Interpretation
± 0.50 to ± 1.00	Large	High positive/negative correlation
± 0.30 to $\pm .49$	Medium	Moderate positive/negative correlation
± 0.10 to ± 0.29	Small	Low positive/negative correlation
± 0.01 to ± 0.09	Negligible	Slight positive/negative correlation
1	1.00-1.80	Strongly Disagree
	0.0	No correlation

DATA PRESENTATION AND ANALYSIS

The data are presented following the statement of the problems of the current study. The study aimed to answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents’ perceived level of instructional leadership in terms of:
 - 1.1 curriculum content and pedagogy;
 - 1.2 planning, assessment, and reporting; and
 - 1.3 personal growth and professional development?

Table 1: Teachers’ perceived level of instructional practices in terms of curriculum content and pedagogy

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Teaches accurate and updated content using appropriate approaches and strategies.	4.73	0.471	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Demonstrates model lessons applying appropriate approaches/strategies to meet students’ diverse learning needs.	4.68	0.511	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Utilizes technology resources in planning, designing, and delivering the lesson.	4.65	0.521	Strongly Agree	Very High

4. Models in utilizing varied techniques and strategies suited to different kinds of learners.	4.62	0.568	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Facilitates students in participating actively in the learning tasks with some levels of independence.	4.69	0.507	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Guides students in showing appropriate behavior of individualism, cooperation, and competition in classroom interaction.	4.74	0.466	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Models in providing appropriate intervention activities for learners at risk.	4.64	0.544	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Facilitates learning using appropriate innovative teaching strategies.	4.58	0.576	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Guides colleagues in school towards improving their competencies in terms of curriculum content and pedagogy through technical assistance/learning action cell.	4.48	0.666	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Support colleagues to align standards, curricula, and instructional strategies.	4.55	0.649	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.64	0.452	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 1 show that teachers' perceived instructional leadership practices in terms of curriculum content and pedagogy are consistently rated at a Very High level, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.64 (SD = 0.452) and all ten indicators described as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated practices include guiding students toward appropriate classroom interaction behaviors (AWV = 4.74, SD = 0.466) and teaching accurate and updated content using appropriate approaches and strategies (AWV = 4.73, SD = 0.471), which suggests strong emphasis on both content integrity and learner behavior support in the teaching-learning process. Although still very high, the comparatively lowest indicator is guiding colleagues through technical assistance/LAC to improve competencies (AWV = 4.48, SD = 0.666), indicating slightly greater variation when the practice involves structured peer-support roles. It means that teachers strongly demonstrate leadership through high-quality curriculum delivery, appropriate pedagogy, and learner engagement strategies, and they generally perceive themselves as highly competent in implementing standards-based and learner-centered instruction. It implies that schools may sustain these strengths by institutionalizing more collaborative structures such as regular coaching cycles, Learning Action Cell (LAC) facilitation, and peer mentoring so that excellent classroom practices are more consistently transferred to colleagues, especially since the peer-guidance indicators, while still very high, show relatively more variability.

The current finding is supported by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017), who emphasize that effective teaching improvement is strengthened through content-focused professional learning and classroom-embedded practices that refine pedagogy. The current finding is also supported by Kraft et al. (2018), who found that coaching and instructional support meaningfully improve teachers' instructional practice aligning with the high ratings on modeling lessons, using varied strategies, and supporting colleagues toward instructional alignment.

Table 2: Teachers' perceived level of instructional practices in terms of on planning, assessment, and reporting

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Uses appropriate formative and summative tests congruent to the lesson.	4.85	0.356	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Uses non-traditional authentic assessment techniques when needed.	4.55	0.579	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Keeps accurate records of learners' performance levels.	4.82	0.412	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Uses expanded time for remediation/enrichment activities based on the results.	4.58	0.594	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Recognizes students' individual differences and provides activities for remediation, reinforcement, and enrichment.	4.73	0.493	Strongly Agree	Very High

6. Guides colleagues in school towards improving their competencies in terms of planning, assessing, and reporting learners' outcomes through the technical assistance/learning action cell.	4.55	0.615	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Regularly assess student learning and ensure specific, timely feedback to students regarding feedback.	4.69	0.485	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Facilitates the conduct of the Parents-Teacher conference.	4.80	0.402	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Conducts an analysis of students' test results for the purpose of improving performance outcomes.	4.75	0.461	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Conducts action research on students' learning outcomes and achievement.	4.40	0.749	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.67	0.398	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 2 show that teachers' perceived instructional leadership practices in terms of planning, assessment, and reporting are rated at a Very High level, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.67 (SD = 0.398) and all indicators described as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated practices include using appropriate formative and summative tests congruent to the lesson (AWV = 4.85, SD = 0.356) and keeping accurate records of learners' performance levels (AWV = 4.82, SD = 0.412), indicating that teachers consistently apply assessment tools aligned with learning objectives and maintain systematic documentation of learner progress. High ratings were also observed in practices that emphasize inclusive assessment and learning support, such as recognizing individual differences and providing remediation, reinforcement, and enrichment (AWV = 4.73, SD = 0.493) and assessing student learning with timely feedback (AWV = 4.69, SD = 0.485), showing that assessment results are used to guide instructional decisions and learner support. It means that teachers demonstrate strong competence and leadership in implementing assessment-driven instruction, ensuring accurate reporting systems, and applying intervention strategies based on learners' needs. It implies that schools in the division can further strengthen these already high practices by sustaining structured assessment literacy initiatives, strengthening data-driven decision-making routines (e.g., item analysis and feedback protocols), and encouraging wider engagement in evidence-based improvement activities such as action research, which remains the comparatively lowest-rated item (AWV = 4.40, SD = 0.749) despite still being very high.

The current finding is supported by the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017), which emphasizes assessment and reporting competencies as a core expectation of teachers under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Pastore et al. (2023), who highlight that strong assessment literacy involves using appropriate tools, interpreting results, and applying evidence to improve instruction skills that align with the teachers' very high ratings on assessment use, record keeping, feedback, and data analysis.

Table 3: Teachers' perceived level of instructional practices in terms of personal growth and professional development

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Maintains stature and behavior that upholds the dignity of teaching.	4.84	0.367	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Manifests personal qualities like enthusiasm, flexibility, caring attitudes, and others.	4.83	0.376	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Uses self-assessment to enhance strengths and correct one's weaknesses.	4.75	0.437	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Participates actively in professional organizations.	4.72	0.453	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Demonstrates desirable personal characteristics of honesty, integrity, dedication, courtesy, and human relations.	4.80	0.402	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Establishes leadership, stress tolerance, fairness, justice, proper attire, and good grooming.	4.67	0.471	Strongly Agree	Very High

7. Demonstrates willingness to improve/develop professional skills through INSET and seminars.	4.82	0.385	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Attends and actively participates in seminars/trainings/workshops sponsored by the Department of Education.	4.79	0.410	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Helps in the preparation of the yearly/growth plan for new learning based on the analyses of the School Improvement Plan and the Annual Implementation Plan.	4.67	0.554	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Shows willingness to enroll in Graduate Studies and Post-Graduate Studies.	4.69	0.507	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.76	0.349	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 3 indicate that teachers’ perceived instructional leadership practices in terms of personal growth and professional development are rated at a Very High level, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.76 (SD = 0.349) and all indicators described as Strongly Agree. The highest-rated indicators are maintaining stature and behavior that upholds the dignity of teaching (AWV = 4.84, SD = 0.367) and manifesting positive personal qualities such as enthusiasm, flexibility, and caring attitudes (AWV = 4.83, SD = 0.376), showing that respondents strongly value professional ethics, personal integrity, and positive teacher disposition. Similarly, high ratings for participation in INSET/seminars (AWV = 4.82, SD = 0.385) and attending DepEd-sponsored trainings (AWV = 4.79, SD = 0.410) suggest that teachers actively engage in continuous learning opportunities to improve professional skills. It means that the respondents demonstrate a strong commitment to professional ethics and continuous development, reflecting a high level of professionalism and readiness to improve through reflection, training, and further education. It implies that the Schools Division of Dapitan City can sustain and strengthen this culture of growth by institutionalizing reflective practice systems (e.g., professional learning communities and mentoring), providing consistent access to relevant trainings, and supporting teachers’ graduate studies through flexible learning arrangements and capacity-building opportunities linked to school improvement priorities (SIP/AIP).

The current finding is supported by the Department of Education (DepEd, 2017), which emphasizes continuous professional growth and professionalism through the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. OECD (2019), which highlights that ongoing professional development and active participation in learning opportunities are essential dimensions of teacher professionalism that contribute to improved teaching practice and school improvement.

Table 4: Summary of the teachers’ perceived level of instructional leadership practices

Descriptors	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Curriculum Content and Pedagogy	4.64	0.452	Strongly Agree	Very High
B. On Planning, Assessment, and Reporting	4.67	0.398	Strongly Agree	Very High
C. Personal Growth and Professional	4.76	0.349	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.69	0.379	Strongly Agree	Very High

SD-Standard Deviation

Table 4 summarizes that teachers’ perceived level of instructional leadership practices is consistently Very High across all three indicators, with all domains described as Strongly Agree. Among the three areas, Personal Growth and Professional Development obtained the highest mean (M = 4.76, SD = 0.349), followed by Planning, Assessment, and Reporting (M = 4.67, SD = 0.398), while Curriculum Content and Pedagogy registered a slightly lower but still Very High mean (M = 4.64, SD = 0.452). It means that the teacher-respondents strongly perceive themselves as consistently demonstrating instructional leadership not only through classroom-based practices (curriculum and pedagogy, assessment and reporting) but also through sustained professionalism and continuous growth, with the strongest emphasis placed on professional values and development. It implies that the Schools Division can sustain and further institutionalize these strengths by strengthening school-based professional learning systems (e.g., mentoring and LAC sessions, assessment literacy initiatives, and structured reflective practice), while giving additional attention to deepening curriculum-and-pedagogy support where variability is relatively higher, to ensure that high standards remain consistent across teachers and schools.

The current finding is supported by Department of Education (DepEd, 2017), which emphasizes that teachers are expected to demonstrate high standards in content and pedagogy, assessment and reporting, and professional development as reflected in the Philippine Professional

Standards for Teachers. It is also supported by OECD (2019), which highlights that continuous professional learning and strong instructional practices are key characteristics of effective teaching and leadership cultures in schools.

2. What is the respondents' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of:

- 2.1 subject matter skills;
- 2.2 teaching strategies skills;
- 2.3 classroom management skills; and
- 2.4 evaluation skills?

Table 5: Teachers' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of subject matter skills

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Provides a comprehensive and accurate grasp of the subject matter.	4.76	0.455	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Applies content of knowledge beyond his/her area of specialization.	4.77	0.472	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Integrates subject matter into other fields of knowledge.	4.78	0.465	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Manifests confidence and firmness with every piece of information given in the class.	4.72	0.498	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Provides students with varied learning experiences for intellectual development.	4.73	0.493	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Possesses the skill in the science and art of questioning.	4.64	0.563	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Cites intra and interdisciplinary content relationship.	4.66	0.538	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Motivates learners in investigating a learning area to expand their knowledge and satisfy their curiosity	4.69	0.507	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Reflects mastery of the entire subject being taught.	4.76	0.455	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Provides opportunities for students to practice and apply learning in real-life situations.	4.80	0.428	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.73	0.426	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 5 reveal that teachers' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of subject matter skills is Very High, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.73 (SD = 0.426) and all indicators rated Strongly Agree. This pattern indicates a consistently strong perception of content mastery and the ability to use subject knowledge effectively in classroom instruction. The highest-rated indicator is providing opportunities for students to practice and apply learning in real-life situations (AWV = 4.80, SD = 0.428), followed closely by integrating subject matter into other fields of knowledge (AWV = 4.78, SD = 0.465) and applying content knowledge beyond one's specialization (AWV = 4.77, SD = 0.472), suggesting that teachers not only know the subject content well but also connect it meaningfully across disciplines and authentic contexts. Meanwhile, although still very high, the relatively lowest-rated item is possessing the skill in the science and art of questioning (AWV = 4.64, SD = 0.563), indicating slightly greater variability in advanced questioning techniques compared with other subject-mastery behaviors.

It means that the teacher-respondents strongly perceive themselves as competent in subject matter mastery, interdisciplinary integration, and the application of knowledge to real-life learning experiences—competencies that support meaningful and standards-based instruction. It implies that schools should sustain these strengths by continuing content-focused professional learning and collaborative planning that reinforces interdisciplinary teaching and authentic applications of learning, while also strengthening higher-order questioning skills through coaching, lesson study, and training on inquiry-based questioning strategies to further enhance classroom discourse.

The current finding is supported by DepEd (2017), which emphasizes content knowledge and its application within and across curriculum areas under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Guerriero (2017), who explains that teacher competence depends on strong pedagogical and content knowledge that enables teachers to make sound instructional decisions and improve student learning.

Table 6: Teachers’ perceived level of teaching competence in terms of teaching strategies skills

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Provides a comprehensive and accurate grasp of the subject matter.	4.76	0.477	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Applies content of knowledge beyond his/her area of specialization.	4.79	0.459	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Integrates subject matter into other fields of knowledge.	4.80	0.428	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Manifests confidence and firmness with every piece of information given in the class.	4.76	0.477	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Provides students with varied learning experiences for intellectual development.	4.77	0.472	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Possesses the skill in the science and art of questioning.	4.68	0.531	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Cites intra and interdisciplinary content relationship.	4.71	0.503	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Motivates learners in investigating the learning area to expand their knowledge and satisfy their curiosity.	4.74	0.466	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Reflects mastery of the entire subject being taught.	4.68	0.551	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Provides opportunities for students to practice and apply learning in real-life situations.	4.81	0.445	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.75	0.426	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 6 indicate that teachers’ perceived level of teaching competence in terms of teaching strategies skills is Very High, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.75 (SD = 0.426) and all indicators rated Strongly Agree. Generally, the responses suggest that teachers consistently apply effective instructional strategies that support learner engagement, knowledge application, and meaningful learning experiences. The highest-rated indicator is providing opportunities for students to practice and apply learning in real-life situations (AWV = 4.81, SD = 0.445), followed by integrating subject matter into other fields of knowledge (AWV = 4.80, SD = 0.428) and applying content knowledge beyond one’s specialization (AWV = 4.79, SD = 0.459). These results imply that teachers frequently use strategies that encourage authentic learning and interdisciplinary connections. Meanwhile, the relatively lowest-rated indicators though still very high include possessing the skill in the science and art of questioning (AWV = 4.68, SD = 0.531) and reflecting mastery of the entire subject being taught (AWV = 4.68, SD = 0.551), showing slightly more variation in questioning techniques and in perceived overall mastery-related strategy use. It means that the respondents strongly perceive themselves as highly competent in using varied teaching strategies, particularly those that promote authentic application of learning, interdisciplinary integration, and learner motivation. It implies that schools should sustain these strengths through continuous professional learning and collaborative lesson planning, while also strengthening advanced instructional questioning and inquiry-based approaches through coaching, demonstration teaching, and Learning Action Cell (LAC) sessions, since effective questioning is essential for developing higher-order thinking and deeper classroom discourse.

The current finding is supported by Darling-Hammond, Hyler, and Gardner (2017), who emphasize that effective teaching is enhanced when teachers develop and apply instructional strategies through content-focused and practice-based professional development. Kraft, Blazar, and Hogan (2018), whose meta-analysis shows that coaching improves instructional practice, reinforcing the value of sustained support in refining teaching strategies and questioning techniques.

Table 7: Teachers’ perceived level of teaching competence in terms of classroom management skills

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Utilizes class periods productively.	4.80	0.452	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Maintains students’ interest and active participation in the class discussion.	4.80	0.428	Strongly Agree	Very High

3. Maintains a classroom atmosphere that is friendly and cooperative to enhance the learning process.	4.82	0.412	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Comes always ready and prepared adequately for every day's learning activities.	4.71	0.503	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Establishes authority in the classroom effectively by making students obey rules and regulations set forth.	4.80	0.452	Strongly Agree	Very High
6. Helps students' group work run smoothly and effectively.	4.78	0.442	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Comes to class early and leaves on time.	4.72	0.498	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Promotes respect for cultural differences in the classroom.	4.79	0.435	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Ensures orderliness and cleanliness in class.	4.80	0.428	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Provides equal opportunities for students to participate actively in class.	4.80	0.428	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.78	0.389	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 7 show that teachers' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of classroom management skills is Very High, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.78 (SD = 0.389) and all indicators rated Strongly Agree. This suggests that the respondents consistently demonstrate strong classroom management practices that support productive learning time, positive classroom climate, and active student participation. The highest-rated indicator is maintaining a classroom atmosphere that is friendly and cooperative to enhance the learning process (AWV = 4.82, SD = 0.412), while several indicators share similarly high ratings, such as utilizing class periods productively (AWV = 4.80, SD = 0.452), maintaining students' interest and active participation (AWV = 4.80, SD = 0.428), ensuring orderliness and cleanliness (AWV = 4.80, SD = 0.428), and providing equal opportunities for students to participate (AWV = 4.80, SD = 0.428). Although still very high, the comparatively lowest-rated indicator is coming always ready and prepared adequately for every day's learning activities (AWV = 4.71, SD = 0.503), indicating slightly more variation in daily preparedness compared with other management behaviors. It means that the teacher-respondents strongly perceive themselves as highly competent in managing classrooms through time management, learner engagement, rule implementation, cooperative learning facilitation, inclusivity, and maintaining an orderly learning environment. It implies that schools should sustain these strengths by reinforcing consistent routines and positive discipline practices, while providing continued support for lesson preparation and classroom organization through collaborative planning, mentoring, and professional learning communities to ensure that high classroom management quality remains consistent across teachers and daily teaching demands.

The current finding is supported by Korpershoek et al. (2016), who found that effective classroom management strategies positively influence students' academic and behavioral outcomes. Bozkus (2021), who highlights that classroom management remains a central teaching competency because it shapes classroom climate and supports effective implementation of instruction.

Table 8: Teachers' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of evaluation skills

Descriptors	AWV	SD	Description	Interpretation
1. Evaluates students' performances fairly and uses adequate and accurate standards and measures of evaluation.	4.83	0.376	Strongly Agree	Very High
2. Uses rubrics for scoring and evaluation.	4.77	0.448	Strongly Agree	Very High
3. Evaluates the performance of the students based on the course objectives and most essential learning competencies through discussions, activities, and quizzes.	4.77	0.424	Strongly Agree	Very High
4. Exercises no favoritism.	4.79	0.481	Strongly Agree	Very High
5. Provides corrective feedback remedies in oral and written responses.	4.73	0.471	Strongly Agree	Very High

6. Provides evaluative activities appropriate to students' abilities, interests, and needs.	4.76	0.431	Strongly Agree	Very High
7. Employs varied forms of evaluation tools.	4.73	0.471	Strongly Agree	Very High
8. Allow students to assess their own performances using appropriate rubrics in some of the activities in the class.	4.75	0.483	Strongly Agree	Very High
9. Conducts remedial instruction and enhancement to improve students' performance.	4.72	0.476	Strongly Agree	Very High
10. Utilizes evaluation and performance results as a basis for improving instruction.	4.79	0.410	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.76	0.382	Strongly Agree	Very High

AWV-Average Weighted Value, SD-Standard Deviation

The results in Table 8 show that teachers' perceived level of teaching competence in terms of evaluation skills is Very High, with an overall mean of AWV = 4.76 (SD = 0.382) and all indicators rated Strongly Agree. This indicates that the respondents consistently practice fair, standards-based, and learning-oriented evaluation. The highest-rated indicator is evaluating students' performances fairly using adequate and accurate standards and measures (AWV = 4.83, SD = 0.376), which highlights a strong commitment to objectivity and credibility in assessment. High ratings were also observed in using rubrics for scoring and evaluation (AWV = 4.77, SD = 0.448) and evaluating performance based on course objectives and the most essential learning competencies (MELCs) through appropriate learning tasks (AWV = 4.77, SD = 0.424), suggesting that teachers strongly align evaluation practices with required learning standards. While still very high, the comparatively lowest-rated indicator is conducting remedial instruction and enhancement to improve students' performance (AWV = 4.72, SD = 0.476), indicating slightly more variation in follow-through actions after evaluation. It means that the teacher-respondents strongly perceive themselves as competent in applying fair and objective evaluation, using rubrics and varied tools, providing feedback, and using results to improve instruction core practices that promote credible grading and continuous learning improvement. It implies that schools sustain this strong evaluation culture by reinforcing assessment literacy programs (e.g., rubric design, feedback strategies, and results interpretation) and by strengthening systematic remediation and enrichment mechanisms (e.g., structured intervention schedules and monitoring of learning gains), since evaluation is most impactful when results lead to targeted instructional adjustments and learner support.

The current finding is supported by DepEd (2017), which emphasizes assessment and reporting competencies under the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. Pastore et al. (2023), who highlight that teacher assessment literacy includes selecting appropriate tools, applying valid criteria, interpreting results, and using assessment evidence to improve instruction skills that align with the respondents' very high ratings on fairness, rubric use, feedback, and data-driven improvement.

Table 9: Summary of the teachers' perceived level of teaching competence

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description	Interpretation
A. Subject Matter Skills	4.73	0.426	Strongly Agree	Very High
B. Teaching Strategies Skills	4.75	0.426	Strongly Agree	Very High
C. Classroom Management Skills	4.78	0.389	Strongly Agree	Very High
D. Evaluation Skills	4.76	0.382	Strongly Agree	Very High
Overall	4.76	0.382	Strongly Agree	Very High

SD-Standard Deviation

Table 9 summarizes that teachers' perceived level of teaching competence is consistently Very High across all four indicators, with all domains described as Strongly Agree. Among the indicators, Classroom Management Skills obtained the highest mean (M = 4.78, SD = 0.389), followed by Evaluation Skills (M = 4.76, SD = 0.382) and Teaching Strategies Skills (M = 4.75, SD = 0.426), while Subject Matter Skills recorded the lowest but still Very High mean (M = 4.73, SD = 0.426). The overall mean of teaching competence is also Very High (M = 4.76, SD = 0.382), indicating a strong and consistent perception of competence across content knowledge, pedagogy, classroom management, and evaluation practices. It means that the teacher-respondents view themselves as highly competent in essential teaching functions, with particularly strong confidence in managing the classroom learning environment and implementing fair and standards-based evaluation. It implies that the Schools Division may sustain these strengths by continuing targeted professional learning that reinforces high-quality instruction, classroom management, and assessment

literacy, while also strengthening deeper content-pedagogy integration and advanced teaching strategies through collaborative lesson study, mentoring, coaching, and professional learning communities to keep competence consistent and responsive to evolving curriculum demands.

The current finding is supported by DepEd (2017), which emphasizes that teachers are expected to demonstrate competence in content knowledge and pedagogy, learning environment, and assessment and reporting as articulated in the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers. It is also supported by Guerriero (2017), who highlights that teacher competence involves the integration of pedagogical knowledge and professional skills that guide effective teaching decisions and classroom practice.

3. Is there a significant relationship between the respondents' perceived level of Instructional leadership practices and the respondents' perceived level of teaching competence?

Table 10: Test of the relationship between the teachers' perceived level of instructional leadership practices and teaching competence

Variables Correlated	rho-value	p-value	Interpretation
Teachers' Instructional Leadership Practices and Teachers' Teaching Competence	0.851	0.000	high positive Large correlation Significant

Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

Table 10 presents the test of relationship between the teachers' perceived level of instructional leadership practices and teaching competence. The result shows a rho-value of 0.851, which indicates a high positive correlation, and a p-value of 0.000 or $p < 0.001$, which is lower than the 0.05 level of significance. This means that the relationship between instructional leadership practices and teaching competence is statistically significant. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the teachers' perceived level of instructional leadership practices and teaching competence is rejected. This means that teachers who demonstrate higher levels of instructional leadership practices also tend to show higher levels of teaching competence. Specifically, when teachers actively engage in curriculum content and pedagogy, planning, assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development, they are also more likely to demonstrate stronger subject matter skills, teaching strategies, classroom management skills, and evaluation skills. The high positive correlation suggests that instructional leadership and teaching competence move together in a strong and meaningful way. This implies that strengthening instructional leadership practices among teachers may help improve teaching competence. School heads and Master Teachers may therefore sustain and enhance programs such as mentoring, coaching, demonstration teaching, Learning Action Cell sessions, classroom observation feedback, assessment support, and professional development activities. Since the relationship is strong and significant, instructional leadership may serve as an important school-based support mechanism for improving teachers' classroom practices and overall instructional quality.

The current finding is supported by Darling-Hammond, Hyler, and Gardner (2017), who emphasized that effective professional development, particularly when content-focused, collaborative, and supported by feedback, improves teachers' instructional practice. The current finding is also supported by Kraft, Blazar, and Hogan (2018), who found that instructional coaching has meaningful positive effects on teachers' classroom instruction, suggesting that leadership practices involving guidance, feedback, and mentoring are closely linked to better teaching competence. Furthermore, the current finding is supported by Nguyen et al. (2020), who reported that instructional leadership dimensions such as monitoring instruction and promoting professional development are positively related to teachers' competence, reinforcing the idea that leadership focused on teaching and learning strengthens teachers' instructional capacities.

DISCUSSION

The findings of the study revealed that the teachers of Dapitan City National High School demonstrated a very high level of instructional leadership practices and teaching competence. In terms of instructional leadership, personal growth and professional development obtained the highest rating, followed by planning, assessment, and reporting, and curriculum content and pedagogy. This indicates that the teachers strongly manifest professionalism, commitment to continuous learning, active participation in trainings, and readiness to improve their instructional practices. Their high rating in planning, assessment, and reporting also shows that they are capable of preparing appropriate assessments, keeping accurate records of learner performance, providing feedback, and using assessment results to improve instruction. Similarly, the very high level of curriculum content and pedagogy suggests that teachers are able to deliver accurate and updated content, apply appropriate teaching approaches, use technology in instruction, and support learners' diverse needs. These findings imply that the teachers are not only focused on classroom teaching but also demonstrate leadership behaviors that contribute to instructional improvement and professional collaboration within the school.

The study also found that the respondents' teaching competence was very high across all indicators, particularly in classroom management skills, evaluation skills, teaching strategies skills, and subject matter skills. This means that the teachers are highly capable of managing classroom routines, maintaining a positive and orderly learning environment, promoting student participation, and applying fair and standards-based evaluation practices. Their strong competence in teaching strategies and subject matter skills further indicates that they can integrate content across disciplines, provide meaningful learning experiences, and connect lessons to real-life situations. Moreover, the study revealed a strong, positive, and significant relationship between instructional leadership practices and teaching competence. This means that teachers who demonstrate stronger instructional leadership practices also tend to exhibit higher teaching competence. The result suggests that instructional leadership plays an important role in strengthening teachers' classroom performance, especially when teachers engage in mentoring, coaching, demonstration teaching, assessment support, professional learning, and reflective practice. Therefore, sustaining school-based professional development programs, Learning Action Cell sessions, peer mentoring, and technical assistance activities is essential in maintaining and further improving teachers' instructional leadership and teaching competence.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it is concluded that the teachers of Dapitan City National High School demonstrated a very high level of instructional leadership practices and teaching competence. Their strong performance in curriculum content and pedagogy, planning, assessment and reporting, and personal growth and professional development shows that they are capable of leading instructional improvement and supporting effective teaching and learning. Likewise, their very high competence in subject matter skills, teaching strategies skills, classroom management skills, and evaluation skills indicates that they possess the necessary knowledge, skills, and professional behaviors needed to deliver quality instruction. Furthermore, the significant and high positive relationship between instructional leadership practices and teaching competence confirms that teachers who demonstrate stronger instructional leadership also tend to exhibit higher teaching competence. This means that instructional leadership is an important factor in strengthening teachers' classroom practices and overall instructional quality. Therefore, continuous mentoring, coaching, professional development, Learning Action Cell sessions, and technical assistance should be sustained to further enhance teachers' instructional leadership and teaching competence.

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